

MORPHOLOGY OF EYEBALL AND EYELID EPITHELIAL TUMORS IN DIFFERENT STAGES OF GLAUCOMA.

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Relevance of the topic: Among ophthalmological diseases, glaucoma is a neurodegenerative disease that leads to a gradual loss of vision, in the pathogenesis of which, along with increased intraocular pressure, morphofunctional changes in the sclera tissue play an important role. At the same time, the trophic state of the eyelid skin and epithelial structures may change at different stages of glaucoma, creating a morphological basis for the development of epithelial tumors. This issue has been poorly studied in the field of ophthalmology, and its comprehensive morphological analysis is urgent.

The aim of the study: the aim of the study was to evaluate the morphological changes of sclera and eyelid epithelial tumors at different stages of glaucoma.

Materials and methods of the study: Biopsies of scleral tissue and eyelid epithelial tumors taken from patients who underwent surgery for glaucoma stages I–IV were used as the study material. During the study, histological analysis was performed using hematoxylin-eosin staining. Morphometric parameters were assessed by collagen fiber thickness, fibroblast density, and the degree of epithelial cell atypia.

Results of the study: According to the results of the study, in the early stages of glaucoma, collagen fibers were regenerated in the sclera and the activity of fibroblasts increased. In the late stages of the disease, sclerosis, hyalinosis and microcirculatory changes were detected. Epithelial hyperplasia, acanthosis, and in some cases signs of cell atypia were observed in eyelid epithelial tumors. In the advanced stages of glaucoma, a tendency of increased proliferative activity was noted in epithelial tumors.

Conclusion: in conclusion, it can be said that morphological changes in the sclera of the eye at different stages of glaucoma affect the trophic state of the epithelial structures of the eyelid. The identified morphological features are a significant and important factor in the early diagnosis and prevention of eyelid epithelial tumors in patients with glaucoma.

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